

Cytoskeletal defects associated with colitogenic WASP mutation.

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Mutation of the genes of the WASP complex are associated with the development of inflammatory bowel disease in humans. We defined the molecular consequences of expression or mutation of WASH complex genes in human cells using whole transcriptome technologies. We report here activation of kinesin motor proteins *KIF20A* and *KIF18B* in induced pluripotent stem cells derived from humans with defined mutation in the Wiskott Aldrich Syndrome genes.

Citations

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